

**THE DISTRIBUTIONS OF HIGH MOMENTS OF CUSP FORM
COEFFICIENTS OVER ARITHMETIC PROGRESSIONS**

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Abstract

Let f be a normalized primitive holomorphic cusp form of even integral weight k for the full modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$. Denote by $\lambda_f(n)$ the n th normalized Fourier coefficient of f . In this paper, we are interested in an asymptotic formula for the sum $\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \equiv l \pmod{q}}} \lambda_f^{2j}(n)$, where $j \geq 5$ is any positive integer, and q is a prime with $(l, q) = 1$.

1. Introduction

The Fourier coefficients of modular forms are important and interesting objects in number theory. Let H_k^* be the set of all normalized primitive holomorphic cusp forms of even integral weight $k \geq 2$ for the full modular group $\Gamma = SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$. Then

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the Hecke eigenform $f(z) \in H_k^*$ has the following Fourier expansion at the cusp ∞ :

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \lambda_f(n) n^{\frac{k-1}{2}} e^{2\pi i n z}, \quad \Im(z) > 0,$$

where $\lambda_f(n)$ is the n th normalized Fourier coefficient (Hecke eigenvalue) such that $\lambda_f(1) = 1$. Then $\lambda_f(n)$ is real and satisfies the multiplicative property

$$\lambda_f(m)\lambda_f(n) = \sum_{d|(m,n)} \lambda_f\left(\frac{mn}{d^2}\right),$$

where $m \geq 1$ and $n \geq 1$ are positive integers. In 1974, P. Deligne [8] proved the Ramanujan–Pettersson conjecture

$$|\lambda_f(n)| \leq d(n), \tag{1}$$

where $d(n)$ is the divisor function. By Inequality (1), Deligne’s bound is equivalent to the fact that there exist $\alpha_f(p), \beta_f(p) \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying

$$\alpha_f(p) + \beta_f(p) = \lambda_f(p), \quad \alpha_f(p)\beta_f(p) = |\alpha_f(p)| = |\beta_f(p)| = 1. \tag{2}$$

More generally, for all positive integers $l \geq 1$, one has

$$\lambda_f(p^l) = \alpha_f(p)^l + \alpha_f(p)^{l-1}\beta_f(p) + \cdots + \alpha_f(p)\beta_f(p)^{l-1} + \beta_f(p)^l.$$

In 1927, Hecke [11] proved that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f(n) \ll x^{\frac{1}{2}}. \tag{3}$$

Later, the upper bound in Inequality (3) was improved by several authors (see, for example, [8, 14, 37]). In particular, Wu [40] has shown that

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f(n) \ll x^{\frac{1}{3}} \log^{\rho} x,$$

where

$$\rho = \frac{102 + 7\sqrt{21}}{210} \left(\frac{6 - \sqrt{21}}{5}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{102 - 7\sqrt{21}}{210} \left(\frac{6 + \sqrt{21}}{5}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} - \frac{33}{35} = -0.118\dots.$$

In the 1930s, Rankin [36] and Selberg [38] independently proved the following asymptotic formula:

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^2(n) = c_f x + O(x^{3/5}), \tag{4}$$

where $c_f > 0$ is a positive constant depending on f , and $\varepsilon > 0$ is an arbitrarily small positive number. Very recently, the exponent in Equation (4) was improved to $\frac{3}{5} - \delta$ in place of $\frac{3}{5}$ by Huang [16], where $\delta \leq 1/560$. This remains the best possible result.

Later, based on work about symmetric power L -functions, Moreno and Shahidi [31] were able to prove $\sum_{n \leq x} \tau_0^4(n) \sim c_1 x \log x$, as $x \rightarrow \infty$, where $\tau_0(n) = \tau(n)/n^{\frac{11}{2}}$ is the normalized Ramanujan tau-function, and $c_1 > 0$ is a positive constant. Obviously, Moreno and Shahidi's result also holds true if we replace $\tau_0(n)$ with the normalized Fourier coefficient $\lambda_f(n)$.

Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform and denote its n th normalized Fourier coefficient by $\lambda_f(n)$. Define

$$S_j(f; x) = \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^j(n),$$

where $j \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and $x \geq 1$.

Based on the work of Moreno and Shahidi concerning the symmetric power L -functions $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ for $j = 1, 2, 3, 4$, Fomenko [9] established the following estimates

$$S_3(f; x) \ll_{f, \varepsilon} x^{5/6+\varepsilon}, \quad S_4(f; x) = c_f x \log x + d_f x + O_{f, \varepsilon}(x^{9/10+\varepsilon}),$$

where $c_f > 0$ and d_f are suitable constants depending on f , and ε is an arbitrarily small positive number. Later, Lü (see, for example, [26, 27, 28]) considered higher moments $S_j(f; x)$ for $3 \leq l \leq 8$, which improved and generalized the work of Fomenko. Later, Lau, Lü and Wu [29] proved that

$$S_j(f; x) = xP_j^*(\log x) + O_{f, \varepsilon}(x^{\theta_j+\varepsilon}), \quad 3 \leq j \leq 8,$$

where $P_j^*(t) \equiv 0$ are zero functions for $j = 3, 5, 7$, and $P_4^*(t), P_6^*(t), P_8^*(t)$ are polynomials of degree 1, 4, 13, respectively, and

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_3 &= \frac{7}{10}, & \theta_5 &= \frac{40}{43}, & \theta_7 &= \frac{176}{179}, \\ \theta_4 &= \frac{151}{175}, & \theta_6 &= \frac{175}{181}, & \theta_8 &= \frac{2933}{2957}. \end{aligned}$$

Lau and Lü [30] derived the general results for $S_j(f; x)$ for all $j \geq 2$ under the assumption that $L(\text{sym}^r f, s)$ is automorphic cuspidal for some positive r . Later, Zhai [42] investigated the higher power moments over the sum of two squares for

$$S_j^*(f; x) = \sum_{a^2+b^2 \leq x} \lambda_f(a^2 + b^2)^j$$

for $2 \leq l \leq 8$. Very recently, Xu [41] improved and extended the above work that the author established on general asymptotics for $S_j(f; x)$ and $S_j^*(f; x)$ for all large

j by utilizing the recent progress that $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ is automorphic for all $j \geq 1$. This is due to the recent celebrated work of Newton and Thorne [33, 34] and some nice analytic properties of these automorphic L -functions.

Andrianov and Fomenko [1] first considered the second power moment of $\lambda_f(n)$ over arithmetic progressions for holomorphic cusp forms. Later, Andrianov [2] improved the error term. Ichihara [18, 19] investigated $\lambda_f^2(n)$ over arithmetic progressions for holomorphic cusp forms for $x \ll q^2$:

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \equiv l \pmod{q}}} \lambda_f^2(n) = \frac{c}{\varphi(q)} \prod_{p|q} (1 - \alpha_f(p)^2 p^{-1})(1 - p^{-1})(1 - \beta_f(p)^2)(1 + p^{-1})^{-1} x + O_{f,\varepsilon}(x^{\frac{3}{5}} q^{\frac{4}{5} + \varepsilon}),$$

where c is some suitable constant depending on f , and $\alpha_f(p), \beta_f(p)$ are the Satake parameters given by Equation (2). Later, Jiang and Lü [21] considered the sum of $\lambda_f^{2j}(n)$ over arithmetic progressions for $j = 2, 3, 4$, respectively. In a similar manner, they also established the corresponding results for the normalized Hecke-Maass cusp form with respect to $SL(2, \mathbb{Z})$ for $j = 2, 3, 4$, respectively.

Very recently, Zou et al. [43] by using the existence of automorphic cuspidal self-dual representation $\text{sym}^j \pi_f$ for all $j \geq 1$ due to Newton and Thorne [33, 34], in combination with some nice properties of the corresponding automorphic L -functions, established the following result.

Theorem 1.1 ([43, Theorem 1]). *Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform and let q be a prime with $(q, l) = 1$. For $j \geq 2$ and $q \leq x^{\frac{3}{4}\vartheta_j}$, one has*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \equiv l \pmod{q}}} \lambda_f^2(n^j) = \frac{c_j x}{\varphi(q)} + O_{f,\varepsilon}(qx^{1 - \frac{3}{2}\delta_j + \varepsilon})$$

for any $\varepsilon > 0$, where $c_j > 0$ are some suitable constants, and $\delta_2 = \frac{92}{597}$ and $\delta_j = \frac{92}{69(j-1)(j+3)+247}$ for $j \geq 3$.

By adopting a similar approach to that given by Theorem 1.1, in this paper we consider the higher moments of cusp form coefficients over arithmetic progressions by adopting the similar approach given by Zou et al. [43]. More precisely, we establish the following result.

Theorem 1.2. *Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform and let q be a prime with $(q, l) = 1$. For $j \geq 5$ and $q \ll x^{\vartheta_j}$, one has*

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \equiv l \pmod{q}}} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) = \frac{x P_{2j}(\log x)}{\varphi(q)} + O_{f,\varepsilon}(qx^{1 - \frac{3}{2}\vartheta_j + \varepsilon})$$

for any $\varepsilon > 0$, and $P_{2j}(t)$ denotes a polynomial of t with degree $\frac{(2j)!}{j!(j+1)!} - 1$, and $\vartheta_j = \frac{92}{69 \cdot 2^{2j} - 23A_j - 6C_j(1) + 4}$ for $j \geq 5$.

Throughout the paper, we always assume that $f \in H_k^*$ is a Hecke eigenform. Let $\varepsilon > 0$ be an arbitrarily small positive constant that may vary in different contexts. The symbol p always denote a prime number.

2. Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce some background on the analytic properties of auto-morphic L -functions and give some useful lemmas which play an important role in the proof of the main result in this paper.

Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform, and let $\lambda_f(n)$ denotes its n th normalized Fourier coefficient. It is natural to define the Hecke L -function $L(f, s)$ associated with f by

$$\begin{aligned} L(f, s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f(n)}{n^s} = \prod_p (1 - \lambda_f(p)p^{-s} + p^{-2s})^{-1} \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 - \frac{\alpha_f(p)}{p^s}\right)^{-1} \left(1 - \frac{\beta_f(p)}{p^s}\right)^{-1}, \quad \Re(s) > 1, \end{aligned}$$

where $\alpha_f(p)$ and $\beta_f(p)$ are the local parameters satisfying Equations (2). The j th symmetric power L -function associated with f is defined by

$$L(\text{sym}^j f, s) = \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m p^{-s})^{-1}, \quad \Re(s) > 1.$$

We may expand it into a Dirichlet series

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^j f, s) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)}{n^s}, \\ &= \prod_p \left(1 + \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p)}{p^s} + \dots + \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p^k)}{p^{ks}} + \dots\right), \quad \Re(s) > 1. \end{aligned}$$

We know that the coefficients $\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n)$ are real, multiplicative functions. For $j = 1$, we have $L(\text{sym}^1 f, s) = L(f, s)$.

It is standard to find that

$$\lambda_f(p^j) = \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p) = \frac{\alpha_f(p)^{j+1} - \beta_f(p)^{j+1}}{\alpha_f(p) - \beta_f(p)} = \sum_{m=0}^j \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m,$$

which can be written as $\lambda_f(p^j) = \lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(p) = U_j(\lambda_f(p)/2)$, where $U_j(x)$ is the j th Chebyshev polynomial of the second kind.

Let χ be a Dirichlet character modulo q . Then we can define the *twisted j th symmetric power L -function* by the Euler product representation with degree $j + 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} L(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s) &:= \prod_p \prod_{m=0}^j (1 - \alpha_f(p)^{j-m} \beta_f(p)^m \chi(p) p^{-s})^{-1} \\ &:= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_{\text{sym}^j f}(n) \chi(n)}{n^s} \end{aligned}$$

for $\Re(s) > 1$.

It is well known that a primitive form f is associated with an automorphic cuspidal representation π_f of $GL_2(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{Q}})$, and hence an automorphic L -function $L(\pi_f, s)$ which coincides with $L(f, s)$. It is predicted that π_f gives rise to a symmetric power lift, an automorphic representation whose L -function is the symmetric power L -function attached to f .

For $1 \leq j \leq 8$, the special Langlands functoriality conjecture states that $\text{sym}^j f$ is automorphic cuspidal, as has been shown by a series of important work of Gelbart and Jacquet [10], Kim [25], Kim and Shahidi [24, 23], Shahidi [39], and Clozel and Thorne [5, 6, 7]. Very recently, Newton and Thorne [33, 34] proved that $\text{sym}^j f$ corresponds with a cuspidal automorphic representation of $GL_{j+1}(\mathbb{A}_{\mathbb{Q}})$ for all $j \geq 1$ (with f being a holomorphic cusp form). Then we know that $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$, where $j \geq 1$, has analytic continuation to the whole complex plane as an entire function and satisfies certain Riemann-type functional equation. We refer the interested readers to [20, Chapter 5] for a more comprehensive treatment.

First, we give the functional equations of the L -functions $L(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s)$ for any $j \geq 1$, which is a special case due to [43, Lemma 3].

Lemma 2.1. *Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform, and let χ be a primitive character modulo a prime q . Then the complete L -function*

$$\Lambda(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s) := q^{(j+1)s/2} \gamma(s) L(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s)$$

can be extended to the whole complex plane as an entire function and satisfies the functional equation

$$\Lambda(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s) = \varepsilon(f, \chi) \Lambda(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \bar{\chi}, 1 - s),$$

where $j \geq 1$ and $|\varepsilon(f, \chi)| = 1$, and $\gamma(s)$ denotes the product of some gamma functions $\Gamma((s + \kappa_n)/2)$, $n = 1, 2, \dots, (j + 1)$, with κ_n depending on the weight of f and the parity of the character χ and $\Re(\kappa_n) \geq 0$.

Lemma 2.2. *For any $\varepsilon > 0$, we have $\int_1^T \left| \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + it\right) \right|^{12} dt \ll T^{2+\varepsilon}$, uniformly for $T \geq 1$, and*

$$\zeta(\sigma + it) \ll (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{13}{42}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon} \tag{5}$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \varepsilon$ and $|t| \geq 1$.

Proof. This first result is given by Heath-Brown [12], and the second result is the recent breakthrough due to Bourgain [4, Theorem 5]. \square

Lemma 2.3. *For any $\varepsilon > 0$, we have*

$$L(\text{sym}^2 f, \sigma + it) \ll (1 + |t|)^{\max\{\frac{27}{20}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon} \tag{6}$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \varepsilon$ and $|t| \geq 1$.

Proof. From the result given by Aggarwal [3, Theorem 1.1], we can easily deduce that

$$L\left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + it\right) \ll (1 + |t|)^{\frac{27}{40} + \varepsilon}. \tag{7}$$

We can obtain the required result from the Phragmén–Lindelöf principle for a strip [20, Theorem 5.53] and the Inequality (7). \square

Lemma 2.4. *Let χ be a primitive character modulo q . For $T \geq 1$ and $q \ll T^2$,*

$$L(\sigma + iT, \chi) \ll_{\varepsilon} (q(1 + |T|))^{\max\{\frac{1}{3}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon} \tag{8}$$

$$L(\sigma + iT, \text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi) \ll_{\varepsilon} (q(1 + |T|))^{\max\{\frac{67}{46}(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon}, \tag{9}$$

and if q is a prime, $\int_0^T |L(\sigma + it, \chi)|^{12} dt \ll_{\varepsilon} q^{4(1-\sigma)} T^{3-2\sigma+\varepsilon}$.

Proof. The results follows from work of Heath-Brown [13], Huang [15] and Motohashi [32], together with the Phragmén-Lindelöf principle for a strip, respectively. \square

From above, we note that the L -functions $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$ and $L(\text{sym}^j f \otimes \chi, s)$ are the general L -functions in the sense of Perelli [35]. For these general L -functions, we have the following individual or averaged convexity bounds.

Lemma 2.5. *Let χ be a primitive character modulo q . For the general L -functions $\mathfrak{L}(s, \chi)$ of degree $2A$ indicated above, we have*

$$\int_T^{2T} |\mathfrak{L}(\sigma + it, \chi)|^2 dt \ll (qT)^{2A(1-\sigma)+\varepsilon} \tag{10}$$

uniformly for $\frac{1}{2} \leq \sigma \leq 1$ and $T \geq 1$. Furthermore,

$$\mathfrak{L}(\sigma + it, \chi) \ll (q(|t| + 1))^{\max\{A(1-\sigma), 0\} + \varepsilon} \tag{11}$$

uniformly for $-\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \varepsilon$.

Proof. This result can be derived by following the similar argument to that used in Zou et al. [43], which was originally deduced from Jiang and Lü [21]. \square

Remark 2.6. For the automorphic L -functions $L(\text{sym}^j f, s)$, where $j \geq 1$, we can regard the modulus q to be 1.

Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform. For $j \geq 2$, define

$$\mathfrak{R}_j(s) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f^j(n)}{n^s}, \quad \Re(s) > 1. \tag{12}$$

Lemma 2.7. *Let $\mathfrak{R}_j(s)$ be defined by Equation (12). For $j = 2n$ with $n \geq 5$, we have*

$$\mathfrak{R}_j(s) = \zeta(s)^{A_n} L(\text{sym}^{2n} f, s) \prod_{1 \leq r \leq n-1} L(\text{sym}^{2r} f, s)^{C_n(r)} H_j(s),$$

where $A_n, C_n(r), (1 \leq r \leq n - 1)$ are given by

$$A_n = \frac{(2n)!}{n!(n+1)!} \quad \text{and} \quad C_n(1) = \frac{3 \cdot (2n)!}{(n-1)!(n+2)!}. \tag{13}$$

The L -function $\mathfrak{R}_j(s)$ is of degree 2^j , all coefficients of $\mathfrak{R}_j(s)$ are nonnegative, the function $H_j(s)$ admits the Dirichlet series which converges absolutely and uniformly in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon$, and $H_j(s) \neq 0$ for $\Re(s) = 1$.

Proof. This result is given by Lau and Lü [30, Lemma 7.1]. \square

Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform and let χ be a Dirichlet character modulo q . For $j \geq 2$, define

$$\mathfrak{F}_j(s, \chi) := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f^j(n)\chi(n)}{n^s}, \quad \Re(s) > 1. \tag{14}$$

Lemma 2.8. *Let $\mathfrak{F}_j(s, \chi)$ be defined by Equation (14). And let χ be a primitive character modulo a prime q . For $j = 2n$ with $n \geq 5$, we have*

$$\mathfrak{F}_j(s, \chi) = L(s, \chi)^{A_n} L(\text{sym}^{2n} f \otimes \chi, s) \prod_{1 \leq r \leq n-1} L(\text{sym}^{2r} f \otimes \chi, s)^{C_n(r)} U_j(s, \chi),$$

where $A_n, C_n(r), (1 \leq r \leq n - 1)$ are suitable constants, and $A_n, C_n(1)$ are the same as in Equation (13). The L -function $\mathfrak{F}_j(s, \chi)$ is of degree 2^j , the function $U_j(s, \chi)$ admits the Dirichlet series which converges absolutely and uniformly in the half-plane $\Re(s) \geq \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon$, and $U_j(s, \chi) \neq 0$ for $\Re(s) = 1$.

Proof. This follows from an argument similar to that of Lau and Lü [30, Lemma 7.1]. \square

3. Proof of Theorem 1.2

In this section, we give the proof of the main result. Firstly, we need the following two important propositions which play an essential role in the proof of the main theorem in this paper.

Let $f \in H_k^*$ be a Hecke eigenform, and let χ be a primitive character modulo a prime q . Define

$$S_j(\chi; x) = \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^{2j}(n)\chi(n), \tag{16}$$

where $j \geq 5$ is any given positive integer.

Proposition 3.1. *Let $S_j(\chi; x)$ be defined as in Equation (16). Then, for $q \ll x^{\vartheta_j}$, we have*

$$S_j(\chi; x) = O_{f,\varepsilon}(qx^{1-\frac{3}{2}\vartheta_j+\varepsilon}), \tag{17}$$

where $\vartheta_j = \frac{92}{69 \cdot 2^{2j} - 23A_j - 6C_j(1)+4}$ for $j \geq 5$, where A_j is given by (13).

Proof. Applying Perron’s formula [20, Proposition 5.54] and Deligne’s bound (2), we obtain

$$S_j(\chi; x) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\varepsilon-iT}^{1+\varepsilon+iT} \mathfrak{F}_{2j}(s, \chi) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O_{f,\varepsilon}\left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T}\right),$$

where $s = \sigma + it$ and $1 \leq T \leq x$ is some parameter to be specified later.

By shifting line of integration to the parallel line with $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon$ and applying Cauchy’s residue theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} S_j(\chi; x) &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon-iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon+iT} + \int_{1+\varepsilon-iT}^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon-iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon+iT}^{1+\varepsilon+iT} \right) \mathfrak{F}_{2j}(s, \chi) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ &\quad + O_{f,\varepsilon}\left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T}\right) \\ &= I_{j,1} + I_{j,2} + I_{j,3} + O_{f,\varepsilon}\left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T}\right), \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

where we have used the fact that $\mathfrak{F}_{2j}(s, \chi)$ has no poles in $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$ and $U_j(s, \chi)$ converges absolutely and uniformly in q for the same region.

For the integrals over the horizontal segments $I_{j,2}$ and $I_{j,3}$, by Inequalities (8), (9)

and (11), along with Lemma 2.8, for $j \geq 5$ and $q \ll T^2$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{j,2} + I_{j,3} &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} x^\sigma |\mathfrak{F}_{2j}(s, \chi)| T^{-1} d\sigma \\
 &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon}^{1+\varepsilon} x^\sigma \left| L(s, \chi)^{A_j} L(\text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi, s)^{C_j(1)} L(\text{sym}^{2j} f \otimes \chi, s) \right. \\
 &\quad \times \left. \prod_{2 \leq r \leq j-1} L(\text{sym}^{2r} f \otimes \chi, s)^{C_j(r)} \right| T^{-1} d\sigma \\
 &\ll \max_{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1+\varepsilon} x^\sigma (qT)^{(2^{2j-1} - \frac{1}{6}A_j - \frac{1}{23}C_j(1))(1-\sigma)+\varepsilon} T^{-1} \\
 &\ll \frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T} + x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} q^{2^{2j-2} - \frac{1}{12}A_j - \frac{1}{46}C_j(1)+\varepsilon} T^{2^{2j-2} - \frac{1}{12}A_j - \frac{1}{46}C_j(1)-1+\varepsilon},
 \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

where $A_j, C_j(1)$ are defined as in Equation (13).

For the integral over a vertical segment $I_{j,1}$, by Lemma 2.4, Lemma 2.8 and Inequality (10), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{j,1} &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \sup_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \mathfrak{F}_{2j} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it, \chi \right) \right| dt \right\} \\
 &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \sup_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it, \chi \right)^{A_j} \right|^6 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{6}} \right. \\
 &\quad \times \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L \left(\text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right)^{C_j(1)} \right|^3 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \\
 &\quad \times \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \prod_{2 \leq r \leq j-1} L \left(\text{sym}^{2r} f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right)^{C_j(r)} \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \left. \times L \left(\text{sym}^{2j} f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left. \right\} \\
 &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \sup_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \left(\left| L \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + iT_1, \chi \right) \right|^{6A_j-12} \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \times \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it, \chi \right) \right|^{12} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{6}} \\
 &\quad \times \left(\left| L \left(\text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{3C_j(1)-2} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \times \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L \left(\text{sym}^2 f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \times \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \prod_{2 \leq r \leq j-1} L\left(\text{sym}^{2r} f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it\right)^{C_j(r)} \right. \right. \\ & \left. \left. \times L\left(\text{sym}^{2j} f \otimes \chi, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it\right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \} \\ \ll & x^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon} q^{2^{2j-2} - \frac{1}{12}A_j - \frac{1}{46}C_j(1) + \frac{1}{69} + \varepsilon} T^{2^{2j-2} - \frac{1}{12}A_j - \frac{1}{46}C_j(1) - \frac{68}{69} + \varepsilon}. \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

By inserting the Equations (19) and (20) into Equation (18), we obtain Equation (17) by taking

$$T = x^{\frac{138}{69 \cdot 2^{2j} - 23A_j - 6C_j(1) + 4}} / q.$$

Since $q \ll T^2$, we have the required restriction that

$$q \ll x^{\frac{92}{69 \cdot 2^{2j} - 23A_j - 6C_j(1) + 4}}.$$

This completes the proof of the proposition. □

Let χ_0 be a principal character modulo a prime q . Define

$$S_j(\chi_0; x) = \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) \chi_0(n), \tag{21}$$

where $j \geq 5$ is any given positive integer.

Proposition 3.2. *Let $S_j(\chi_0; x)$ be defined as in Equation (21). Then for $q \ll x$,*

$$S_j(\chi_0; x) = xP_{2j}(\log x) + O(x^{\kappa_j + \varepsilon}),$$

where $P_{2j}(t)$ denotes a polynomial of t with degree $\frac{(2j)!}{j!(j+1)!} - 1$, and $\kappa_j = 1 - \frac{420}{2^{2j+1} \cdot 105 - 80A_j - 63C_j(1) + 62}$.

Proof. Define

$$\mathfrak{R}_j(s, \chi_0) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\lambda_f^{2j}(n) \chi_0(n)}{n^s} = \mathfrak{R}_{2j}(s) H(s, \chi_0), \tag{22}$$

where $\mathfrak{R}_{2j}(s)$ is given by Lemma 2.7, and $H(s, \chi_0)$ is a finite Euler product which does not equal 0 for $\Re(s) > \frac{1}{2}$.

Applying Perron's formula [20, Proposition 5.54] and Deligne's bound (2), we obtain

$$S_j(\chi_0; x) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{1+\varepsilon-iT}^{1+\varepsilon+iT} \mathfrak{R}_j(s, \chi_0) \frac{x^s}{s} ds + O_{f,\varepsilon} \left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T} \right),$$

where $s = \sigma + it$ and $1 \leq T \leq x$ is some parameter to be specified later.

By shifting the line of integration to the parallel line with $\Re(s) = \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon$ and applying Cauchy’s residue theorem, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} S_j(\chi_0; x) &= \frac{1}{2\pi i} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon - iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + iT} + \int_{1 + \varepsilon - iT}^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon - iT} + \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + iT}^{1 + \varepsilon + iT} \right) \mathfrak{R}_j(s, \chi_0) \frac{x^s}{s} ds \\ &\quad + \text{Res}_{s=1} \left\{ \mathfrak{R}_j(s, \chi_0) \frac{x^s}{s} \right\} + O_{f,\varepsilon} \left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T} \right) \\ &:= J_{j,1} + J_{j,2} + J_{j,3} + xP_{2j}(\log x) + O_{f,\varepsilon} \left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T} \right), \end{aligned} \tag{23}$$

where $P_{2j}(t)$ denotes a polynomial of t with degree $A_j - 1$, and A_j is given by (13).

For the integrals over the horizontal segments $J_{j,2}$ and $J_{j,3}$, by Equations (5), (6), and (11), (22), together with Lemma 2.7, for $j \geq 5$ and $q \ll T^2$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} J_{j,2} + J_{j,3} &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon}^{1 + \varepsilon} x^\sigma |\mathfrak{R}_{2j}(s, \chi_0)| T^{-1} d\sigma \\ &\ll \int_{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon}^{1 + \varepsilon} x^\sigma \left| \zeta(s)^{A_j} L(\text{sym}^2 f, s)^{C_j(1)} L(\text{sym}^{2j} f, s) \right. \\ &\quad \times \left. \prod_{2 \leq r \leq j-1} L(\text{sym}^{2r} f, s)^{C_j(r)} \right| T^{-1} d\sigma \\ &\ll \max_{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon \leq \sigma \leq 1 + \varepsilon} x^\sigma T^{(2^{2j-1} - \frac{4}{21} A_j - \frac{3}{20} C_j(1))(1-\sigma) + \varepsilon} T^{-1} \\ &\ll \frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T} + x^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon} T^{2^{2j-2} - \frac{2}{21} A_j - \frac{3}{40} C_j(1) - 1 + \varepsilon}, \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

where $A_j, C_j(1)$ are defined as in Equation (13).

For the integral over a vertical segment $J_{j,1}$, by Lemma 2.2, Lemma 2.3 and Inequality (10), we have

$$\begin{aligned} J_{j,1} &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon} \log T \sup_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \mathfrak{R}_j \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right| dt \right\} \\ &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon} \log T \sup_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{A_j} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{6}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L \left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{C_j(1)} dt \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \\ &\quad \times \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \prod_{2 \leq r \leq j-1} L \left(\text{sym}^{2r} f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{C_j(r)} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. \times L \left(\text{sym}^{2j} f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left. \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} \log T \sup_{1 \leq T_1 \leq T/2} \left\{ \frac{1}{T_1} \left| \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + iT_1 \right) \right|^{6A_j-12} \right. \\
 &\quad \times \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \zeta \left(\frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{12} dt \Bigg\}^{\frac{1}{6}} \\
 &\quad \times \left(\left| L \left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{3C_j(1)-2} \int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| L \left(\text{sym}^2 f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^2 dt \right)^{\frac{1}{3}} \\
 &\quad \times \left(\int_{T_1}^{2T_1} \left| \prod_{2 \leq r \leq j-1} L \left(\text{sym}^{2r} f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^{C_j(r)} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \times L \left(\text{sym}^{2j} f, \frac{1}{2} + \varepsilon + it \right) \right|^2 dt \Bigg)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Bigg\} \\
 &\ll x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{2^{2j}-2-\frac{2}{21}A_j-\frac{3}{40}C_j(1)-\frac{389}{420}+\varepsilon}. \tag{25}
 \end{aligned}$$

By inserting the Equations (24), (25) into Equation (23), we obtain

$$S_j(\chi_0; x) = xP_{2j}(\log x) + O\left(\frac{x^{1+\varepsilon}}{T}\right) + O\left(x^{\frac{1}{2}+\varepsilon} T^{2^{2j}-2-\frac{2}{21}A_j-\frac{3}{40}C_j(1)-\frac{389}{420}+\varepsilon}\right). \tag{26}$$

On taking

$$T = x^{\frac{420}{2^{2j+1} \cdot 105 - 80A_j - 63C_j(1) + 62}}$$

in Equation (26), we obtain the desired result. □

Proof of Theorem 1.2 We are now able to prove Theorem 1.2. Let q be a Dirichlet character modulo a prime q . By the orthogonality relation of Dirichlet characters, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \equiv l \pmod{q}}} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) &= \frac{1}{\varphi(q)} \sum_{\chi \pmod{q}} \bar{\chi}(l) \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) \chi(n) \\
 &= \frac{1}{\varphi(q)} \sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) \chi_0(n) + O\left(\sum_{n \leq x} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) \chi(n)\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that $\varphi(q) = q - 1$ since q is a prime.

From Propositions 3.1 and 3.2 and noting that $1 - \frac{3}{2}\vartheta_j > \kappa_j$ for $j \geq 5$, we have

$$\sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ n \equiv l \pmod{q}}} \lambda_f^{2j}(n) = \frac{xP_{2j}(\log x)}{\varphi(q)} + O_{f,\varepsilon}(qx^{1-\frac{3}{2}\vartheta_j+\varepsilon}).$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 1.2. □

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